

INSULIN THERAPY

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Abstract: Hypoglycemic coma is considered the most formidable complication of insulin therapy. One of the reasons is an overdose of the drug.

Lipodystophia is a complication that occurs when the technique of insulin therapy is not followed.

Insulin resistance - develops as a result of long-term use of insulins of the same type. To avoid such complications, it is recommended to change drugs every 3 months.

Keywords: Insulin, bolus insulin therapy, Actrapid, Gensulin, Lizpro

Physiology of insulin

Insulin (from the Latin language -insula - means island) - is produced by the cells of the islet of Langerhans of the pancreas. The insulin molecule is of a protein nature and is formed by two polypeptide chains containing 51 amino acids.

History of insulin

Insulin 1921 was first synthesized by Banting and Best.

The first injection of insulin was made in 1922 and since then there have been many varieties of this hormone.

Insulins differ from each other in duration and mechanism of action.

Types of insulin

Bovine insulin is synthesized from the pancreas of cattle and differs from human insulin in 3 amino acids. For this reason, it often causes allergic reactions.

Pork insulin is synthesized from the pancreas of pigs and is structurally very similar to human insulin. Differs in only one amino acid. It does not cause allergic reactions, unlike bovine, and is easily tolerated.

Analog insulin

Human insulin - that is, their analogues are synthesized by genetic engineering. Analogue insulins are synthesized by exposure to E. Koli, as well as by the replacement of one amino acid in porcine insulin. The melon species is widespread and easily applied in practice.

Modern classification

According to the new classification, 2 types of insulin are divided.

Long-acting insulins (basal insulin) - they replenish the daily dose of insulin

Short-acting insulin (bolus insulin) - which replenishes postprandial insulin secretion (secretion after a meal).

Groups of insulins

Short-acting insulins, in turn, are divided into 2 types:

insulin regular

Ultrashort-acting insulins

This group of drugs are peak insulins, after s / c administration, they begin their action after 30 minutes and reach a peak after 2 hours. Their duration is 6 hours. It is recommended to administer the drug 30-40 minutes before a meal or during a meal.

Short-acting insulin analogues

Human insulins (genetically engineered) - Actrapid HM,

Bioinsulin R, Gansulin R, Gensulin R,

Insuran R, Rinsulin R, Humulin Regular.

Human insulins (semi-synthetic) - Biogulin R, Humodar R.

Soluble insulin (monocomponent porcine) - Actrapid MS, Monodar, Monosuinsulin MK.

Ultrashort-acting insulins

Preparations of this group begin their action 15 minutes after s / c injection. The peak of action is reached after 2 hours, and the duration is 4 hours.

Representatives: insulin

Lizpro (Humalog)

Insulin aspart (NovoRapid

Penfill, NovoRapid FlexPen).

Insulin glulisin (Apidra).

Basal insulin

Basal insulins are divided into medium-acting and long-acting insulins. Each of these groups, in turn, is subdivided into peak and non-peak.

Intermediate-acting insulins are activated 2 hours after administration, the peak is reached by 6-8 hours, the duration is 12 hours.

Biosulin N, Gansulin N,

Gensulin N, Insuman Bazal GT, Insuran NPH,

Protafan NM, Rinsulin NPH, Humulin NPH.

Insulin isophane.

Mixed insulins

Insulins containing in their composition both short-acting and long-acting insulin in a ratio of 30/70.

30% - short-acting insulin

70% long-acting insulin

It is advisable to use them in type 2 diabetes s / c 2 times a day.

NovoMix 30 Penfill, NovoMix 30 FlexPen, Mixtard 30 NM, Humulin M3.

Methods of insulin therapy

Basal bolus insulin therapy

It consists of 5 single doses of insulin: 3 I.K.D during meals and 2 I.D.D in a ratio of 70/30 of the daily requirement.

30% Actrapid(i.k.d),

70% Gensulin N (i.d. d).

Conventional insulin therapy is more often recommended for type 2 diabetes. They differ in 2 single injections of insulins k.d and d.d in the same ratio - 30\70.

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